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A Review of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Education during the Digital Era

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Artificial intelligence (AI) plays a critical role in education. This paper aims to review the artificial intelligence adoption in learning and teaching during the digital era.

Method: A narrative synthesis and a systematic literature review were conducted in this review article. The literature and information were obtained from various books and research articles on EBSCO, Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, and ScienceDirect. The inclusion criteria were studies that clearly defined artificial intelligence in the education sector, were published

and written in English and were peer-reviewed. Five independent reviewers assessed search results, extracted data, and set the studies' quality to summarise and report the findings.

Result: Artificial intelligence has already entered the education sector. Implementing artificial intelligence is a strategic and critical factor in educational development. Furthermore, artificial intelligence is increasingly being used as a digital assistant. They assist teachers and students in various ways, including giving students access to a wide range of learning materials based on their specific learning needs and subjects. However, some risks are associated with artificial intelligence advancements, such as safety, security, and privacy concerns. As a result, artificial intelligence technologies positively and negatively affect the education sector.

Conclusion: Artificial intelligence technologies have positive and negative effects on education. Thus, it is critical to prioritise artificial intelligence in education and implement appropriate strategies to meet teachers' and students' needs and expectations through AI technologies. As a result, academic performance will be excellent.

Recommendation & Implication: Qualitative research, such as interviews, or quantitative analysis, such as online questionnaires, may be developed in the future to provide more explanations and explicit findings. The implications could be applied to school administrators, teachers, and students to understand better and implement appropriate strategies to improve educational performance through AI.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence (AI), Education, Digitalisation, Technology, Review*

INTRODUCTION

In this modern era of the industrial revolution 4.0, almost all activities of human life cannot be separated from the use of information technology (IT) as an enabler for other activities and services. IT is no longer just a tool and is now a required component that must be owned. Its advancement, which significantly facilitates human life activities, has resulted in a high reliance on the existence of information technology (Rahmatullah et al., 2022). In addition, since technology plays a much more significant role in the digital era than it did in previous generations, today's generation is technologically literate. The rise in literacy, combined with recent technological advancements, has resulted in expanding technology in education. These are the generations entering the classroom today, ranging from millennials to Gen-Z, and they all share distinct characteristics that define their age. These generations expect to be actively engaged in their learning and do not perform well as passive learners. As a result, technology must be embraced in today's education, and teachers must incorporate technology into their students' learning (Hashim, 2018). The use of IT in the implementation of education by a modern educational institution at the level of a world-class university has become an obligation,

given that the performance of education in the context of public services necessitates good governance that ensures transparency, accountability, efficiency, and effectiveness of education. Because of the awareness of the importance of information and communication technology (ICT), which is one of the main pillars of human civilisation's development today, the seriousness of management underpins the application of ICT in the implementation of all educational activities (Rahmatullah et al., 2022). Rapid advances in big data and artificial intelligence technologies have profoundly impacted all aspects of human society, including the economy, politics, science, and education (Luan et al., 2020). Artificial intelligence (AI), a machine-based technique with algorithmic power for making predictions, diagnoses, recommendations, and decisions, has gained prominence in the educational community in recent years due to its potential to support learning in various contexts. With diverse applications such as intelligent tutors for content delivery, feedback provision, and progress supervision, the field of AI in education has demonstrated technological advances, theoretical innovations, and successful pedagogical impact (Chen et al., 2022). Therefore, the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) in the education industry is a critical topic.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial intelligence (AI) technology has a long history and is constantly changing and growing. It focuses on intelligent agents, devices that perceive their surroundings and take actions to maximise their chances of success (Shabbir & Anwer, 2018). The term "artificial intelligence" conjures up images of supercomputers, which are computers with enormous processing capabilities, including adaptive behaviour, such as the inclusion of sensors and other stuff that allow them to have human-like cognition and functional abilities, and thus improve the supercomputer's interaction with humans (Chen et al., 2020). Artificial intelligence is the ability of a computer program to learn and think. Everything that involves a program doing something that people would typically think would require the intelligence of a human is considered artificial intelligence (Mitchell, 2019). Furthermore, artificial intelligence is the simulation of human intelligence operations by computers, specifically computer systems. AI excels at specific tasks and changes almost every sector of a country's economy by allowing computers to make sound decisions that lead to more efficient operations (Dong et al., 2020; Limna, 2022). AI has been applied in many practical fields. In addition, intelligent computers are transforming society as computers and robots become more intelligent. AI is now present in almost every aspect of people's daily life (Li et al., 2018). AI also allows people to work smarter, which leads to better business outcomes. Still, it also necessitates the development of new competencies and capabilities, ranging from technological expertise to social and emotional skills, as well as creative abilities (Limna, 2022). The benefits of AI are enormous, and it has the potential to revolutionise any professional sector (Makridakis, 2017). Hence, the adoption of artificial intelligence is regarded as critical in industry 4.0. Since its inception, it has brought numerous opportunities and challenges to various sectors. Many AI-powered

technologies have been developed with the potential to significantly improve the economy by improving the quality of life in many sectors (Limna et al., 2021).

Artificial Intelligence in Education

Over the last twenty-five years, there has been significant progress in AI in education (Roll & Wylie, 2016). AI has been widely used in education since the advancement of computing and information processing techniques. AI in education creates new opportunities, potentials, and challenges in educational practices (Ouyang & Jiao, 2021). AI in education focuses on making significant advances in educational techniques through real-world trials and the development of standard modular prototypes in statistical reasoning, data visualisation, and learning analytics (Alam, 2021). One of the most important goals of AI in education is to provide personalised learning guidance or support to individual students based on their learning status, preferences, or personal characteristics (Hwang, 2014; Hwang et al., 2020). AI in education also aims to use AI to facilitate the instruction process (e.g., understanding and facilitating computer-supported collaborative learning through discourse analysis and achieving performance prediction through educational data mining), during which instructors are critical, and their acceptance of AI is vital. However, since AI is a relatively new concept for instructors, less-experienced instructors frequently struggle to execute effective, on-the-spot responses to analytics from AI-enabled applications, resulting in their reluctance and lower acceptance of AI. Thus, improving instructors' acceptance of AI systems appears critical (Chen et al., 2022). Academics, educators, policymakers, and professionals must work together to address the new opportunities and challenges of the big data explosion and AI revolution. They must collaborate to develop all learners' necessary competencies and skills for twenty-first-century work, driven by the knowledge economy (Luan et al., 2020).

The adoption of AI in education has created new opportunities for developing more effective learning activities and better technology-enhanced learning applications or environments. There are several essential aspects of AI technology in education, such as teacher feedback, automatic grading system, adaptive learning, distance learning, and so on (Hwang et al., 2020; Yufeia et al., 2020). Teacher feedback is the student evaluation of the teacher. It is a feedback method that has long been used in education. Despite the transition from paper to online surveys, little progress has been made in feedback. Because student evaluation of teaching is frequently the most valuable source of information, it must be prioritised. Modern technologies, such as AI-powered conversation robots, machine learning, and natural language processing offer exciting opportunities to improve feedback quality (Holstein et al., 2019; Peters, 2019). The automatic grading system is a professional computer program based on AI that simulates a teacher's behaviour to assign grades to student tasks in an educational setting. It evaluates student knowledge, analyses responses, provides feedback, and creates personalised training programs. This program is used in many artificial intelligence education apps. The system automatically provides the learner evaluation score during the learning test. This method can assist teachers in better understanding their students' learning situations while students are

more aware of their learning achievement and mastery of knowledge (Yufeia et al., 2020). AI is also critical in distance learning. The application of AI in distance education attempts to explore the use of computers to bridge the gap between students and educators. Artificial intelligence technology can support distance education, or different intelligent systems can be used to improve distance education (Kose, 2014).

Benefits and Challenges of Artificial Intelligence in Education

The advantages of AI applications in education are vast and varied (Owoc et al., 2019). Many educational settings are increasingly deploying several AI applications powered by machine-learning systems and algorithms, such as personalised learning systems, automated assessments, social media sites, and predictive analytics tools. These AI applications have shown promise in assisting teachers and students in several ways, including providing instruction in mixed-ability classrooms, providing students with detailed and timely feedback on their writing products, relieving teachers of the burden of knowing everything and giving them more room to support their students while they are observing, discussing, gathering information in their collaborative knowledge-building processes, and so on (Akgun & Greenhow, 2021; Miao et al., 2021). Social networking sites connect students and teachers through social media outlets, such as Facebook. Social media integration can promote students' active learning, collaboration skills, and connections with communities outside the classroom. Chatbots can also be found on social media platforms due to the various AI systems (Kim et al., 2019; Krutka et al., 2019). Personalised learning systems, also known as adaptive learning platforms or intelligent tutoring systems, are typical and valuable applications of AI to support students and teachers. These applications give students access to various learning materials based on their specific learning needs and subjects (Akgun & Greenhow, 2021). Adaptive learning is also one of the most promising benefits of AI in education. While the traditional classroom education model continues to be one-size-fits-all, AI-powered adaptive learning systems are designed to maximise learning efficiency (Owoc et al., 2019).

Despite these advantages, there are some legitimate concerns. One primary concern is privacy. The invasion of privacy and the uncertainty posed by AI are critical issues on the negative side of technological implementation in ridesharing (Cheng et al., 2022). Data governance is concerned with the system of data organisation, collection, control, storage, usage, archival, and destruction. Establishing data governance is driven by a specific program, supported by clear policies and procedures, and communicated by organisational leadership and management. In general, the regulations must provide all the necessary means to maintain the generic requirements, which include accessibility, availability, completeness, accuracy, integrity, consistency, auditability, and security (Owoc et al., 2019). The effective use of big data analytics and AI depends on the applicability of the factors involved with each technology. The individual's knowledge and analytical skills are commensurate with those required to use extensive data analysis to facilitate analysis and decision-making (Tong-On et al., 2022).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Narrative synthesis is the process of reviewing related literature and synthesis of findings from multiple studies that typically depend on words and text to clarify and explain the synthesis's findings (Jaipong et al., 2022; Limna, 2022). The typical starting point for qualitative content analysis is to systematically transform a large amount of text into a highly organised and concise summary of key findings (Siripipatthanakul & Bhandar, 2021). This review article carried out a narrative synthesis and a systematic literature review. Moreover, five databases were searched for this systematic review: PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, and ScienceDirect. The inclusion criteria were studies that clearly defined artificial intelligence in the education sector, were published and written in English and were peer-reviewed. Five independent reviewers evaluated search results, extracted data, and assessed the quality of included studies to summarise and report the findings.

RESULT

Artificial intelligence (AI) has already infiltrated the education sector. The use of AI is a strategic and critical factor in educational development. Furthermore, AI technologies are increasingly being used as digital assistants. They help teachers and students in various ways, such as providing students with access to different learning materials based on their specific learning needs and subjects. However, some risks are associated with AI advancements, such as safety, security, and privacy concerns. As a result, AI technologies have positive and negative effects on the education sector.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

AI technology has a long history and is constantly continuing to evolve. Ouyang and Jiao (2021) indicated that since the advancement of computing and information processing techniques, AI has been widely used in education as it opens new possibilities, possibilities, and challenges in educational practices. Owoc et al. (2019) confirmed that AI technologies impact teaching and learning, both positively and negatively, in the education industry. Hwang et al. (2020) and Yufeia et al. (2020) indicated that using AI in education had opened new avenues for developing more effective learning activities and better technology-enhanced learning applications or environments. There are several essential aspects of AI technology in education, such as teacher feedback, automatic grading systems, and adaptive learning. Akgun and Greenhow (2021) revealed that AI applications give students access to various learning materials based on their specific learning needs and subjects. Kose (2014) stated that AI technology could be used to support distance e improve distance education when combined with other intelligent systems. Also, Owoc et al. (2019) indicated that the data governance of AI is concerned with the design of data organisation, collection, control, storage, usage, archival, and destruction. Cheng et al. (2022) also concluded that one primary concern for AI technologies is privacy. Consequently, AI technologies have both positive and negative

consequences. Thus, it is critical to prioritise AI in education and implement appropriate strategies to meet the needs and expectations of teachers and students using AI technologies. As a result, high academic performance will occur.

LIMITATION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study employed a narrative synthesis method. Quantitative research, such as questionnaires, regarding AI in the education sector, is recommended for future research. A qualitative approach, such as interviews, could provide a clear picture of insight results.

IMPLICATION

This review article may lead to a better understanding of AI adoption in the education sector. As a result, the implications could be applied to school administrators, teachers, and students to understand better and implement appropriate strategies to improve educational performance through AI in education.

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